

Hamiltonian Path Principle on Integral Circuits

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ABSTRACT

We give the notion to the experimental part of research in our investigation of the “P versus NP” theorem and the optimization principle within the physical layout.

EXPERIMENT

We build the integral circuit on a board and give the experimental projection of the abstract processes and processes which are put in a different environment, or physically.

The VLSI devices are used today in many aspects [1].

Hamiltonian is met in the Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) [2] where it defines the shortest possible path visiting each of the city once. TSP by itself was an argument of “P versus NP” theory and practice [3].

On the experimental electrical board we build the layered circuit by using elements for satisfying the “visit-once” condition. Thus, the shortest path of a limited number of mediate elements can be found.

CONCLUSION

We have presented the experimentation theory for which there could be conjectured that each of the shortest paths found on the simulated integral circuit can form the Hamiltonian by itself in its decomposed state.

REFERENCES

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